

ANTIBIOTICS SELECTED TO BE REPURPOSED AS ANTICANCER AGENTS TO COMBAT LUNG CARCINOMA

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Abstract. *Identifying new anticancer drugs with unique modes of action has emerged as a serious scientific problem. As a result, the prospect of repurposing antibiotics as anticancer drugs has been investigated. Anticancer antibiotics are substances produced by microorganisms with anticancer activity, principally peptides and anthraquinones, that have a clear and effective effect on preventing cancer from growing uncontrollably, aggressively, and spreading. Anticancer antibiotics include mitomycin, anthracyclines, actinomycin, bleomycin, endiayne and guanorycin. Antibiotics can induce cancer cell death, inhibit cancer cell division, and prevent cancer metastasis. Antibiotics have anticancer properties and may lead cancer cells to die. Despite the introduction of high-throughput sequencing technology in recent years, the possible negative effects of antibiotics on cancer therapy through microbial imbalance have been primarily ignored. Antibiotics in cancer treatment: investigate their potential mechanisms and provide strategies to mitigate the possible adverse effects of antibiotics.*

Keywords: *Antibiotics; Cancer therapy; Cancer*

Introduction

Cancer is a common and frequently encountered disease that poses a major risk to human health. According to modern cell biology, the basic mechanisms include aberrant cell development and migration with an unregulated cell cycle, continual self-renewal, and cancer stem cell reproduction [1]. Every year, more than eight million people die from cancer, putting a significant strain on global economic and social development. Surgery, radiation, chemotherapy, immunotherapy, and targeted therapy are currently used to combat cancer [2]. During chemotherapy, a lot of the patient's tumor cells stop responding to the drug. In the field of cancer, drug resistance seems to be a big problem [3]. Antibiotics are secondary metabolites produced by microorganisms (such as bacteria, fungi, and actinomycetes) or higher animals and plants during their lives that have anti-pathogen or other properties that can interfere with the development of other living cells [4]. According to research, antibiotics can increase cancer apoptosis, decrease cancer development, and prevent cancer spread. For these reasons, antibiotics are increasingly being utilised in the treatment of cancer [5]. Anticancer medication resistance is a complex process that starts with changing therapeutic targets. Advancements in DNA microarrays, proteomics, and targeted medicines have enabled novel ways to managing drug resistance. Despite advancements in drug design, there are still no effective treatments for advanced cancers like invasion and metastasis. Cancer cells can become resistant to anticancer treatments due to genetic variations, greater efflux, mutations in drug targets, activation of alternative signaling pathways, accelerated DNA repair mechanisms, multi-drug resistance, inhibition of apoptosis, and epigenetic changes. Potentially new drug discovery process involves computational, exploratory, translational, and clinical investigations to identify medicinal compounds [6]. The importance of antibiotics to

humans prompted the idea of testing them against cancer cells. Anti-cancer antibiotics are known to exert their effects by multiple mechanisms as shown in Figure 1. Mechanistic characterization of effect of antibiotics on Cancer Stem cells is an emerging area of research associated with cancer biology which needs to be further explored.

Figure 1: Antibiotics exert their anticancer effect by different mechanisms. Pro-cancer (+), anti-cancer (-), up-regulated (↑), and down-regulated. (Nilofer Bano, et al., 2024)

REFERENCES:

1. Rajaraman R, Guernsey DL, Rajaraman MM, Rajaraman SR. Stem cells, senescence, neosis and self-renewal in cancer. *Cancer Cell Int.* 2006;6:25. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar] [Ref list]
2. Kanady K E SWU, Zietman A L, Treatment strategies using transurethral surgery, chemotherapy, and radiation therapy with selection that safely allows bladder conservation for invasive bladder cancer[J] 2015;13(5):359-64. [PubMed] [Ref list]
3. Longley, D.B.; Johnston, P.G. Molecular mechanisms of drug resistance. *J. Pathol.* 2005, 205, 275-92.
4. Selim, M. S. M., Abdelhamid, S. A., & Mohamed, S. S. (2021). Secondary metabolites and biodiversity of actinomycetes. *Journal, genetic engineering & biotechnology*, 19(1), 72. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43141-021-00156-9>
5. Goodman, L.S.; Wintrobe, M.M.; Dameshek, W.; Goodman, M.J.; Gilman, A.; McLennan, M.T. Nitrogen mustard therapy: Use of methyl-bis (beta-chloroethyl) aminehydrochloride and tris (beta-chloroethyl) amine hydrochloride for hodgkin's disease, lymphosarcoma, leukemia and certain allied and miscellaneous disorders. *JAMA.* 1946, 132, 126-32.